

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN "THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA" BY ERNEST HEMINGWAY INTO UZBEK

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Abstract: Translating stylistic devices is challenging since they cannot be translated literally if the message is to be fully transferred. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the meaning of the stylistic devices in source language. This article attempts to explore the strategies used in translating the literary devices in "The Old Man and the Sea" by Ernest Hemingway. The author analyses the translation problems of stylistic devices such as metaphors, simile and personification through some examples. The aim is to assess how much of the style and culture of the original has been preserved. It is also concerned with the problem of equivalence and translation units, since equivalence is considered the tool for detailed comparison.

Key words: stylistic devices, simile, metaphor, personification, translation, equivalent, culture.

"The Old Man and the Sea" is undoubtedly Hemingway's masterpiece. It is a simple story about a fisherman Santiago and his battle with a great marlin. For 84 days Santiago does not catch a single fish but he does not feel discouraged. He goes far out into the sea and hooks a giant marlin. A desperate struggle ensues in which Santiago manages to kill the fish and tie it to his boat, only to find that on the way home he has to fight a more desperate struggle with some dangerous giant sharks, which eat up the marlin, leaving only a skeleton. The old man brings it home and goes to bed to dream, almost dead with exhaustion. But his struggle wins him much respect.

Ernest Hemingway was a master in the use of figurative language, and he utilised a wide range of stylistic devices such as epithet, hyperbole, metaphor, personification, and simile to portray the characters of his book. The stylistic devices

are some sort of language tools and techniques, which commonly used by poets and writers in literature. Those devices contribute a great deal in the novelty and uniqueness of language in a given piece of text. In this regard, Simpson (2004) provides the definition of stylistic device “a stylistic device can be any linguistic feature that is unpredictable. It is any linguistic feature which stands in contrast to what is normally used in everyday language” [6].

Metaphor is the figurative language which is used as a means of comparing things that is essentially unlike. In metaphor, the comparison is implied that is, the figurative term is substituted for or identified with the literal term [2]. ‘Metaphor’ is the phenomenon whereby we talk and, potentially, think about something in terms of something else [5]. In the work "The Old Man and the Sea", the writer widely used metaphors to enhance expressiveness and imagery. Translating metaphors can often be a challenging task, as they rely heavily on cultural understanding and can have multiple interpretations. In the case of translating "The Old Man and the Sea" by Ernest Hemingway into Uzbek, there are several specific translation problems that can arise with the metaphors used in the text due to cultural differences, variety of metaphors and fishing terms used in the source language[3]. Some of these translation problems can include:

Cultural differences: The novel is set in a Cuban fishing village and contains various references to Cuban culture, landscapes, and traditions. Translating these cultural aspects into Uzbek may require finding equivalent metaphors that resonate with Uzbek readers. For example, **Age is my alarm clock**[4] - *Men uchun qarilikning o‘zi qo‘ng‘iroq soat*[1]. In this text, the translator uses the literal translation. The metaphor used in this example has a deep meaning. It shows that old age awakens consciousness in a person. Often, the older a person is, the earlier he wakes up. There is no scientific explanation for how this phenomenon occurs. Maybe old people wake up early to get more done for the rest of their lives. For Santiago, old age is a real awakening. And most importantly, he must do something outstanding in life. His feat is that he managed to catch a huge fish and survive alone

from the cruel waves of the sea. It is due to cultural differences that this metaphor is not so clear for Uzbek readers.

Symbolic metaphors: The novel has symbolic metaphors that represent broader themes such as endurance, struggle, and the human condition. Translating these metaphors requires capturing their symbolic significance in a way that resonates with the Uzbek cultural context. For example, *You're with a lucky boat*[4]- *Sen baxti chopgan qayiqda ov qilyapsan*[1]. In this text, the translator uses the method of equivalent translation. The image of the boat in the story can be compared to Charon's boat in ancient Greek mythology. Charon takes dead souls to the shores of the other world on his boat. Therefore, according to philosophy of this myth, sailing across the sea, across the river, across the ocean means sailing across existence to the promised shore. It is the shore of happiness, the shore of hope, and victory.

Here a new symbol is applied - a boat, but it is not an ark. The Ark is a global symbol. All nature on earth can be symbolically perceived as one ark - a receptacle for all biological information. And in this case, you can just talk about the boat, and we are talking about saving only one person, that is, Santiago. However, one person is the representative of all mankind. The salvation of one person is also of great importance. This boat of Santiago was kind, happy, in the sense that it fed him for many years, brought good luck. At least, thanks to this boat, he lived to this age. He has good fame, he has a boy - heir. And it's all thanks to the boat. Then Santiago considers the boat as his friend, as a living being. This boat is a kind of entity for him. And he can talk to the boat as to a living being, which is what happens in the story. As many Uzbek readers follow Islam, it is challenging to translate this metaphor to the target language with its deep meaning.

Specificity of fishing terms: "The Old Man and the Sea" heavily relies on fishing-related metaphors and terminology. Some of these terms may not have direct equivalents in Uzbek, necessitating the translator to find culturally relevant alternatives that convey the essence of the original metaphors. For example, *You can let the cord go, hand, and I will handle him with the right arm alone until you stop*

that nonsense[4] - Sen **chilvirni** qo'yib yuborsang ham bo'lar. *Maynavozchiliging tugamaguncha, o'ng qo'lim bilan evini qilib turaman[1]*. There is a fishing term *cord* in the example above. Such terms are complicated to translators as sometimes they may have various meaning in different contexts. If a translator is not aware of fishing terms, he may easily confuse in the process of translation.

Also, the example above contains a figure of speech called personification because if we analyse the word *nonsense*, it has two meanings: 1) as a connotative meaning - a temporary partial paralysis of habitually or excessively used muscles. 2) as a denotative meaning - spoken or written words that have no meaning or make no sense. When considering any deviation above, there are two meanings of the word *cramp* which is the state of the left hand -it was stiff and cramping, but the translators use the term *maynavozchilik* to represent the state of the left hand, even though the term *maynavozchilik* is a one feeling only felt by human beings. If we categorize the translation, we should say that the translator used a communicative translation technique. Ibrahim Gafurov translated the language and choice of words that are simpler and more easily read and understood by the reader, and the message contained in the phrase could also be easily up to the reader.

Historical and geographical references: "The Old Man and the Sea" contains references to historical events and geographical locations that may not be widely known or significant in Uzbekistan. The translator may need to find alternative metaphors or explanations to ensure comprehension and maintain the intended metaphorical resonance. Hemingway used Spanish words in "The Old Man and the Sea" because he wanted to create a realistic dialogue and realistic interior monologues for the characters in the story. These characters are Cuban, so their native language is Spanish. For example, ***He always thought of the sea as la mar which is what people call her in Spanish when they love her. Sometimes those who love her say bad things of her but they are always said as though she were a woman[4]*** - *U har doim dengizni, unga muhabbat qo'ygan hamma kishilar kabi xayolidan ispanchasiga la mar deb atardi. Ayrim paytlarda dengizga mehr qo'ygan*

odamlar, u haqda badxazm gaplar aytishadi, ammo doimo bu gaplar dengiz emas, go 'yo ayol ustida borayotganga o 'xshaydi[1].

In the example above, the translator uses the method of equivalent translation. Translation conveys both the external and internal content of the original. The author uses verbs that express the behaviour of people in order to show the image of nature more clearly. Through this, the natural phenomenon depicted in the work becomes more vivid in a reader's mind. Santiago always treats the sea with love. He looks at the sea as a woman, who is generous, brings blessings, does good deed to people and at the same time it causes disasters. The old man perceives the sea as a living person and never feels alone during his journey. In short, Santiago loves the sea and is inspired by it. Such ideas show that the work is extremely relevant even today. Especially today's young people, who have indifferent attitude towards nature, can draw the necessary conclusions from this work.

In conclusion, these translation problems highlight the need for a skilled and culturally sensitive translator who can effectively recreate the metaphorical richness of Hemingway's work in Uzbek while considering the cultural nuances of the target language.

References

1. Ernest Xeminguey. Chol va dengiz. Qissa. Ibrohim G'ofurov tarjimasi. – Toshkent, “Yangi asr avlodi” nashriyoti. 2015.
2. Karimov O. “Metafora – poetik tafakkur asosi”. “Jahon adabiyoti”, 2014-yil 8-son.
3. Galperin, I. (1981). Stylistics. Moscow: Higher School.
4. Hemingway, E. (1995). The Old Man and the Sea. New York: Scribner.
5. Semino, E. (2008). Metaphor in discourse. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
6. Simpson, P. (2004). Stylistics: A Resource Book for Students. London and New York, Taylor & Francis Online.